

Quantum Discrete Bound Energies and the Free Particle $\exp(ipx)$

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. And SPN, Messina Nov. 20, 2023

The discrete energy values of quantum bound states are usually said to follow from the mathematical properties of the Schrodinger differential eigenvalue equation with boundary conditions or from the eigenvalues of the Hermitian Hamiltonian matrix. In other words, they appear as mathematical properties. We try to investigate the physical reason for this discreteness and argue that it follows from the discrete $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ units, i.e. half wavelength units found in $\exp(ipx)$. More generally, we try to argue that quantum motion, free or bound, is based on a spatial probabilistic periodicity.

In classical physics and even for a quantum free particle, any momentum value is allowed. A quantum free particle, however, is associated with a half wavelength unit $\frac{1}{2} \hbar p$ and this constraint has consequences if other x constraints exist in a problem. In the case of a bound state, an x constraint enters due to the classical turning points. As a result, we argue that one must consider the two constraints together and this leads to discreteness. Interestingly, a bound state, such as an oscillator, one retains the rough form of crests and troughs, like $\cos(px)$ for a free particle. Thus, the bound state is similar to an altered free particle type periodic pattern. This is in keeping with Newton's view of a particle moving with $v(x)$ in dx in a potential system and also with the correspondence principle. Parity considerations seem to be key in this problem. As a result, we argue it is the free particle nature which continues to manifest itself in a bound problem and this rules out various wavefunction shapes that do not follow the crest-trough pattern, say for an oscillator, even though a Fourier decomposition of the wavefunction allows for any wavefunction shape which respects the boundary conditions.

Classical Physics and a Quantum Free Particle

In classical physics, any positive energy is allowed for in:

$$\frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2 + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

In other words, energy is continuous. Even though the particle accelerates, mathematically one considers, to first order, that in each dx it is a free particle moving with velocity $v(x)$. Thus, the notion of a free particle is present in the bound case of a particle in a potential.

A quantum free particle is described by the wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. This is an eigenfunction of $-i \hbar \frac{d}{dx}$, where $\frac{d}{dx}$ is the translational operator. The center of mass of the particle, so to speak, may be anywhere, yet there is a spatial constraint in the sense that a half wavelength:

$$\frac{1}{2} \hbar p \quad ((2))$$

exists. As a result, any p is allowed and hence any $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ (nonrelativistic energy), but at the same time there exists a spatial constraint given by ((2)). This follows from a probabilistic motion in space associated with constant motion. The probability must die down to zero at two endpoints. In other words, even though p and $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ match classical values, the smallest length associated with a quantum free particle is $\frac{\hbar p}{2}$. In order for this to match Newton's picture, $\frac{\hbar p}{2}$ must be within dx . The real consequence of $\frac{\hbar p}{2}$ from a free particle, however, seems to appear when other spatial constraints exist in a problem. We consider the case of a single particle bound state in this problem.

Infinite Well Potential

We begin with the example of a single well potential because it seems to display the direct relationship between a free quantum particle and its wavelength constraint and a bound particle. A bound quantum particle must have a wavefunction which tends to zero at positive/negative infinite and must satisfy (nonrelativistically) the Schrodinger eigenvalue differential equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W(x) + V(x)W(x) = E_n W(x) \quad ((3))$$

Mathematically, this differential equation, with the boundary equation, leads to a discrete set of E_n (energy), unlike the continuous energy classical case. Alternatively, one may consider the eigenvalues of the Hermitian Hamiltonian (energy) matrix, which are real, positive and discrete. As a result, discrete energy seems to be a mathematical property. We wish, however, to investigate this in more detail.

In principle, one might suggest considering any shape of a wavefunction (a real function for a bound state), as long as it satisfies the boundary conditions and ((3)). At first glance, one would not expect to find a connection with the free particle periodic solution $\exp(ipx)$. The first term on the LHS of ((3)), however, is a kind of average of free particle kinetic energies, which does allow for the possibility of a crest-trough type of solution. In a free particle case, $\exp(ipx) + \sin(ipx) = 2\cos(px)$ which shows the origins of such a periodic type of solution.

In order to see the connection between the free particle, the boundary condition and the wavelength constraint, we examine an infinite well potential. Such a potential introduces a spatial constraint as there can be no wavefunction outside of $(0,L)$, where L is the length of the potential. Inside the particle is free, so one does not have to worry about potential issues. As a result, one has two spatial constraints, the length L and the halfwavelength $\frac{1}{2}h\bar{v}/p$. Even though a quantum free particle may have any p value, the constraint associated with the half wavelength (and the zero values of $\cos(px)$) means that only select free particle $\cos(px)$ are zero at $x=0$ and $x=L$. This free particle wavelength constraint then leads to the discreteness of energy levels in the infinite well potential case. Thus, in this case, one sees clearly that it is the free particle wavelength feature which accounts for discreteness. In this extreme case, the particle is free within $(0,L)$ which is keeping with Newton's picture, as long as one notes that there is a half wavelength constraint associated with such a quantum free particle, so dx values are really equivalent to the half wavelength value. As the energy increases, $h\bar{v}/p$ decreases and dx begins to become very small, i.e. one has the correspondence principle and Newtonian mechanics emerges.

General Potential

A general potential $V(x)$, does exhibit the relationship between a free particle and its half wavelength constraint and boundary conditions as clearly as the infinite well potential. A spatial constraint exists, however, in the problem as spatial probability, and hence the wavefunction, must start to drop off outside the classical turning points. This constraint, by itself, however, only requires a wavefunction (real function) which drops off at the two turning points, Inside, one might guess that any shape is possible and that there is no reason to expect any kind of free particle features. In such a case, $\exp(ipx)$ is simply used in a Fourier decomposition of the wavefunction and any shape satisfying the boundary conditions might hold.

A first possible hint of a problem with such a scenario is that the kinetic energy is an average of free particle kinetic energies. Thus, the notion of a free particle is still very much present. A second problem is that given:

$$P(x) = \text{spatial probability} = W(x)W(x) \text{ where } W(x) \text{ is the wavefunction} \quad ((4))$$

$W(x)$ may be positive or negative. In such a case, a drop at a classical turning point may be associated with either a positive or negative slope. This allows for even and odd parity functions. An odd parity function, however, must have a zero in between the classical turning points. This immediately leads to the notion of periodicity, something that is seen already for the free particle $\cos(px)$ from $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, one starts to see a situation in which a bound solution may represent a kind of distorted periodic type of solution with crests and troughs.

Such a view is in keeping with the correspondence principle and Newton's view. If a periodic type solution exists, then each crest-trough unit may be thought of as a dx value associated with an average p . Given that crest-trough units change in width and height, one has changing p (momentum), i.e. acceleration. Thus, the crest-trough picture leads to Newtonian mechanics when crest-trough units fit into tiny dx lengths, where a tiny dx means that it is very small compared to the length between the classical turning points.

Given the crest-trough pattern, one may use arguments similar to that of the infinite well-potential to describe the discreteness of energy. In both cases of an infinite potential or say an oscillator, one switches from even parity to odd parity solutions and this means a discrete energy jump. It is the again the constraint of the length between the turning points and the half-wavelength type constraint of free motion emerging, we argue.

Parity

The argument suggested above depends heavily on parity, i.e. a changing of sign of $W(x)$, because $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$. This changing of sign is already present in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ of the free particle $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, there seems to be a kind of spatial periodicity associated with quantum motion, whether it be free motion or bound.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the discreteness of bound energy values seems to usually be attributed to the discrete eigenvalues of a Hermitian Hamiltonian matrix or to the solutions of an eigenvalue differential equation with certain boundary conditions, i.e. the function must drop off outside an interval (determined by the classical turning points roughly). Here, we argue that quantum motion seems to be associated with periodicity in space and that this imposes a spatial constraint. A free quantum particle may have any p (momentum) value and so this value and energy are continuous, just as in the classical case. There is nevertheless an inherent spatial constraint linked with the half wavelength $\lambda = hbar/p$. The consequences of this appear explicitly in the case of an infinite well potential existing in $(0,L)$. In order for the wavefunction to disappear at $x=0$ and $x=L$, one must have explicit p free particle values, leading to a discrete energy. One may also notice, that one changes from positive parity to negative as energy increases. Given the constraint $(0,L)$, one must use the half wavelength constraint to see which p values fit in the range.

If one considers a general potential, then the association between free particle periodicity and a solution which satisfies boundary conditions (drops outside classical turning points) does not seem so clear. It is again parity, however, which allows for negative and positive $W(x)$ values. There is no reason not to have both in a single $W(x)$ within the turning point range, and this leads to the possibility of a $W(x)=0$ value and periodicity. Unlike the free particle $\cos(px)$, these crests and troughs have different heights and widths, but periodicity is present nevertheless. Thus, both a free particle and bound particle exhibit spatial periodicity, suggesting that this is part of quantum motion. This behaviour is also in keeping with the correspondence principle and Newtonian mechanics, because as widths of the crest-trough units become very small (i.e. fit into a Newtonian dx), it is as if one has a $\cos(p(x)x)$ in each dx region, i.e. free particle with a different p in each dx , which is the Newtonian picture.